

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 2 - Contractual and financial aspects of cross-service integration

D2.4 Techno-economic feasibility case study across service life cycle

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.4 **Techno-economic feasibility case study** is the fourth deliverable of **WP2 Contractual and financial aspects of cross-service integration** as a result of **Task 2.4 Techno-economic feasibility case study across service life cycle**. It aims at defining the NEON methodology for feasibility assessment and adapting the methodology for the four Citizen Energy Communities under consideration in the NEON project.

Based on the foreseen activities in the NEON framework, the consortium took actions to understand the feasibility and the KPIs of the evolving NEON energy communities. From the selected four communities, CEC-4 (STAINS CITY in France) that is already operational, CEC-2 (Domaine de la Source in France) that has been formed last 21 January 2023, and CEC-1 (BERCHIDDA in Italy) and CEC-3 (Polígono industrial Las Cabezas in Spain) that are still in planning phase.

The feasibility tool proposed in Task 2.4 framework takes into consideration that one CEC can be in different establishment / operational stages, and that different evaluation/assessment tools for planning the next steps of CEC development might be needed.

At first, the feasibility tool was tested in France on various community projects and on NEON CEC-2, the Domaine de la Source. In the NEON framework, the tool was adapted and tested on CEC-1, the pilot of Berchidda, on CEC-3, the pilot of Polígono industrial Las Cabezas, and CEC-4, Stains City. In our opinion, the initial calculations already generated added values to the NEON energy communities. In order to allow an easy adaptation and customization to all the territories, the Excel tool was used. The current version of the tool is not the final one and it will evolve within the NEON framework.

This tool includes several functions:

- Actual energy situation of the buildings (consumption, energy production etc...)
- Possible evolutions of efficiency improvement
- Benefits of energy self-consumption calculation
- Return of investments

The results of the report will be used as input for the last WP2 task, as well as WP4, WP5 and WP6 tasks and will help in focusing the service offer and setting the foundation of contractual and business models to be elaborated further in the project. In addition, results will be reflected in the specification of legal and financial requirements for deployment of the proposed service concepts.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

BESS	Battery energy storage systems
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CEP	Clear Energy Package
CGs	Capacity Guarantees
CNMC	Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y la Competencia / National Markets and Competition Commission
CPI	Consumer Price Index
CRE	Commission de régulation de l'énergie
CTE	Código Técnico de la Edificación / Technical Building Code
DEEP	De-risking Energy Efficiency Platform
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DR	Demand-Response
DRA	Demand Response Aggregator
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EC	European Commission
EDF	Électricité de France
EEB	Energy Efficient Buildings
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ESCo	Energy Service Company
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
GHG	GreenHouse Gas (emission)
GIS	Geographic information system
GSE	Gestore Servizi Energetici / Energy Services Operator
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis

NEBEF	Block Exchange Notification of Demand Response mechanism
OE	Opérateurs d'Effacement
P4P	Pay For Performance
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RTE	Réseau de Transport d'Électricité
TRV	Tarifs Réglementés de Vente de l'électricité

1. Introduction

NEON project aims at developing and establishing a technical and business ecosystem for integrated energy services for European communities, capable of saving energy, reducing CO2 emissions, and bringing economic and social benefits while valorising the energy efficiency and flexibility at demand-side. The project engages a network of stakeholders, service providers and final consumers to establish, in co-creation, the cross-sectorial arrangements and underlying service concepts.

NEON objectives are aligned with the Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity. The internal market for electricity has been progressively implemented throughout the Union since 1999 and it aims to deliver real choice for all Union final customers, be they citizens or businesses, new business opportunities, competitive prices, efficient investment signals and higher standards of service, and to contribute to the security of supply and sustainability. The Directive (EU) 2019/944 [1] introduced the Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) concept as a category of cooperation of citizens or local actors that should be subject to recognition and protection under Union law with the aim to enable faster market uptake, and facilitate communities, both residential and non-residential, in becoming energy efficient. In NEON, the CECs service concepts and business models will be showcased in four CEC setups, see Table 1 (BERCHIDDA in Italy, DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE in France, POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS in Spain and STAINS CITY in France) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 7 “follower” communities will be developed during the project.

Table 1. Overview of NEON CECs activities (status November 2022)

CEC	Operational	NEON Year 1 activities
1- BERCHIDDA in Italy	The CEC is not yet formalised but RES self-consumption at building level is already operational	Recruitment and engagement of citizens and stakeholders Installation of smart meters
2- DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE in France	Formed in January 2023	Awareness raising and financial assessment
3- POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS in Spain	Will be formed	Awareness raising; Technical categorization, API
4 - STAINS CITY in France	Yes	Deployment of services

1.1 Deliverable Objectives

The goal of **Deliverable 2.4 Techno-economic feasibility case study** is to propose a methodology that is suitable for the assessment of CEC activities prior to implementation and putting the CEC in operation, as well as to present the current concrete NEON assessment activities. Deliverable 2.4 builds upon the previous WP1 and WP2 deliverables, in particular

- the technical characterization of CEC energy assets (generation, storage), working profiles, load type (heating/cooling systems, common lightning, etc.), energy requirements and flexibility potential, as well as the building efficiency retrofit, and cross-service integration opportunities identified in **D1.1 (Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes)**;
- the cross-service integration scenarios elaborated in **D1.5 (NEON Platform Architecture and performance assessment KPIs)**;
- the European regulatory framework as well as national regulations affecting NEON presented in **D2.1 Legal and financial framework for cross-service integration**;
- the performance-based contracting techniques (including benefits and risks) analysed in **D2.2 Multi-actor energy performance contracting**;
- and the analysis and identification of suitable financial structures that ensure cost-effectiveness of the service offer and minimize, at the same time, the business risk for the involved actors (see **D2.3 Service financial structure and business risk distribution**).

As presented in Table 1, CEC-4 (STAINS CITY in France) is already operational, CEC-2 was formed in January 2023, while CEC-1 (BERCHIDDA in Italy) and CEC-3 are still in planning phase. Taking into consideration that one CEC can be in different establishment / operational stages, the involved stakeholders (ESCO, investors, end-users) need different evaluation/assessment tools for planning the next steps of CEC development.

Assuming that the regulatory preconditions for operating a CEC are fulfilled, the goal of this deliverable is

- from one side, to define the elements of a CEC **Techno-economic feasibility case study** for long-term building/system operation (typically 10-20 yrs.);
- and from the other, to propose a tool that will serve as a decision support system for optimal CEC development in this phase of NEON project.

From the investors' perspective, the CEC development should take into account the relevant factors for deployment of renewable energy technologies and demand response programs such as geographical location, energy demand requirements, spatial availability, applicable energy pricing schemes, available governmental subsidies (e.g., feed-in-tariffs), etc. Hence, for long-term CEC building/system operation planning, **a methodology is needed that takes into consideration and assesses a number of technical and economic evaluation criteria**. Different evaluation criteria shall be assembled which entail energy efficiency design aspects such as technical (total energy production, imports from grid, etc.), and economic sustainability (NPV and IRR). The CEC operator shall define different yearly decarbonization scenarios (e.g., until 2050), based on the

combination of alternative strategies. The economic performance evaluation resulting from these analyses will support CEC on

- making decision on potential investments;
- approaching potential new CEC members;
- elaboration of a strategy towards 2050 decarbonization.

This deliverable reports about the activities in Task 2.4 framework including the tool developed and tested in CEC-1 by R2M Energy, CEC-2 by ALB, CEC-3 by GFM, and CEC-4 by Engie. Consultation meetings were organized to transfer the methodology from ALB to the other CEC partners (R2M Energy, GFM, and Engie).

A **first step** in applying the methodology is to calculate the energy baseline for the CEC, considering existing members energy use, and associated environmental impacts. This calculation takes into account the current characteristics of buildings and energy systems, energy consumption in each point of use, current renewable energy production, geographically representing the data in a GIS.

1.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable consists of six sections:

- Section 1: Introduction;
- Section 2: Techno-economic feasibility case study;
- Section 3: Feasibility tool (Scope and services of CECs);
- Section 4: Feasibility tool - Implementation aspects;
- Section 5: Economic feasibility; and
- Section 6: Conclusion.

2. Techno-economic feasibility case study

The objective of task 2.4 is to analyse the techno-economic feasibility of integrated energy services and energy efficiency measures under consideration in the four NEON citizen energy communities (CEC).

In the NEON project preparation phase, the NEON servitisation approach was introduced which spans from energy audit over service contracting, energy efficiency interventions to services in operation. It is inspired by EPC life-cycle categorization that can be found in practice. NEON servitisation approach is structured in 4 service life-cycle phases, as follows

- Project identification and preliminary analysis;
- Service contracting and financial structure;
- Building energy efficiency intervention and retrofit;
- Service integration and managing the services in operation.

If we consider the CEC as an **energy community ecosystem**, e.g., see definition¹

“a group of citizens, social entrepreneurs and public authorities who jointly invest in producing, selling and managing renewable energy who are expected to play a prominent role in the energy transition”

different scenarios can be elaborated that reflect the possible ways of evolvement of the ecosystem.

This section documents the approach that was used to initiate the NEON techno-economic feasibility case study in the first year of the NEON project. In our vision, the approach has three aspects, namely technical, financial and computational aspects (as presented in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Technical, financial and computational aspects of the case study

2.1 Assessment of NEON technical arrangements

Tools for techno-economic feasibility analysis and planning the establishment and development of CEC are part of the upper level of the proposed NEON architecture, as presented in Figure 2, see also D1.5. These tools aim at design and retrofit energy infrastructure and provision of optimal topology and sizing of energy assets for a given context and user defined constraints such as geographical location (yielding energy harvesting potential from renewables), required energy demand, applicable energy pricing schemes, available budget etc.

Example of CEC operational data needed for the feasibility analysis

- Building location and characteristics
- Electric mobility rate (%)
- Self-consumption rate (%)
- Rate of local energy consumption (%)
- Self-consumption volume (kWh)
- Grid injection volume (kWh)
- Inflation rate for energy price

Example of CEC regulatory constraints

- In France, the CEC shall be formed in 2 km radius

The planning of CEC energy efficiency measures requires utilization of energy demand simulators and development of underlying algorithms and approaches that determine the energy performance of both residential and non-residential buildings included in the CEC. When it comes to implementation, such simulator or software application shall collect the necessary data and forward it to advanced numerical simulation and/or MCDA or optimization engine. In order to support short, medium, long-term investment decisions for retrofit and/design of new energy infrastructures, the output from such optimization engine shall deliver appropriate technical, and economic performance indicators.

In NEON, in year 1, we have looked for a methodology that may be sufficiently simple to be applied to a large number of buildings (potentially the entire CEC) to model their energy demand, and thus allow for their benchmarking and classification, coincided with the development of energy demand model for the purpose of energy planning.

CEC Data collection

On the technical side, the proposed methodology

- considers data collection and leverages the existing appliances rather than building physics;
- requires actual building consumption data. For this, real or estimated consumption data need to be used. Typically, these may be available in a time interval of one, two, three, months, etc. Obviously, for the method to be used, data, for at least a year, must be available. In addition, besides building level energy bills, other sources of actual energy consumption data, such as smart energy meters, may provide actual consumption data at device level and at various sampling rates, ranging from seconds to days. The estimates of

appliance usage times, required in the previous energy audit method, may be eliminated by “sub-metering” (invoices).

In NEON year 1, we have decided to work on annual averaged data and not data with a finer resolution. Indeed, the solar production forecast is fairly accurate over a long period, while on a small scale it can turn out to be completely wrong. Hence, there is no need in seeking high precision to have accuracy. Finally, we worked on the basis of Excel, to allow easy adaptation and customization to all territories. In addition, the current version, as of the date of the deliverable, is not the final version of the tool because it will evolve in each country in the NEON framework. Similarly, the multi-criteria analysis tool (MCDA) was not implemented because it was unjustified in view of the low complexity of data. However, the possible extension by using multi-criteria analysis is given in Chapter 5. Example of variables included in the building data collection are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Example of building data

Variable type	Variable
Building ID	Building number /name Latitude and Longitude
Apartment ID	Apartment/Office Smartmeter (number) Potential stakeholder (number)
Consumption data	Type of consumption Electricity consumption TOTAL (kWh) Electricity consumption HVAC (kWh) Electricity consumption DHW (kWh) Electricity consumption SPECIFIC (kWh) Gaz Consumption HVAC - DHW (kWh) GAZOIL Consumption Mobility (kWh) Electric mobility consumption (kWh)
Production	Solar Production

Collecting open data (example for France)

Because the NEON CECs are not yet fully operational, the analysis carried out in D2.4 framework (see Sections 3 and 4) is based on existing measurements and additional data supplemented by regional statistical institutes. An example of such data for France is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Example of legal state data (2022 - France)

Base data	Price €/kWh	GeqCO ₂ /kWh (1)	Source
Gazoil for mobility (€/kWh)	0.18784	298	https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/prix-des-produits-petroliers
Electricity peak price HP (€/kWh)	0.14580	12	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=9om9gBs9-ut8a9bWqWwfqhUb5qYpQSm_piNju56jLx8=
Electricity low peak price HC (€/kWh)	0.11490	12	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=9om9gBs9-ut8a9bWqWwfqhUb5qYpQSm_piNju56jLx8=
Grid Consumption base (€/kWh)	0.13740	12	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=9om9gBs9-ut8a9bWqWwfqhUb5qYpQSm_piNju56jLx8=
CEC Grid consumption (€/kWh)	0.14350	12	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=9om9gBs9-ut8a9bWqWwfqhUb5qYpQSm_piNju56jLx8=
CEC self-consumption (€/kWh)	0.01050	50	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf?id=9om9gBs9-ut8a9bWqWwfqhUb5qYpQSm_piNju56jLx8=
Grid injection (€/kWh)	0.09800	50	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000044173060
Gaz HVAC (€/kWh)	0.08100	230	https://gaz-tarif-reglemente.fr/gaz/tarif-reglemente/niveaux-de-prix-par-commune.html?gclid=EAlalQobChMI217kr-ny9wIVVo9oCR1mcgsCEAAYASAAEgle2vD_BwE&gclidsrc=aw.ds
Industrial/Office price of energy (€/kWh)	0.06000	-	-

2.2 Multi-criteria CEC design

NEON is aimed to deliver next-generation integrated energy services for Citizen Energy Communities (CECs). As part of the architecture, the NEON partners have proposed **to maximise the impact of traditional energy efficiency services**, through holistic optimization of building operation and energy asset utilization.

CEC Optimization in NEON

In NEON WP3 framework, two tasks were dedicated to CEC optimization

- **Task 3.3:** Holistic energy dispatch optimization for improved asset scheduling (M10-M21)
- Leader: IMP
- **Task 3.5:** Holistic DR flexibility service through demand-side aggregation (M15-M24) -
Leader: CSEM

The proposed methodology will be enhanced with algorithms that add new design perspectives, as follows.

1. The current approaches typically consider either electric or thermal domain and leverage their methodology on balancing this demand independently with considered energy sources and storages. However, increased utilization of devices like heat pumps, which satisfy thermal demand by contributing to electricity demand, requires an integrated assessment approach.
2. Also, as illustrated in Figure 1, as the CEC evolves, technical categorization will change, by including more components on Level 1 of the architecture (see Figure 3). Hence, the dynamic context, as well the varying energy prices and the dynamics of energy exchange with power grid shall be considered in the techno-economic feasibility study.
3. The application of Demand Response (DR) programs in day-to-day CEC operation has implications on the sizing of individual CEC components (e.g., demand flexibility may reduce the required storages size).

On the economic side, the methodology was extended to consider the required initial investment, operation (e.g., in some cases for building retrofit and smartness upgrade), and maintenance (O&M) costs, and cost of capital, but also the overall process of the CEC life cycle.

CEC multi-criteria decision algorithms

In novel planning tools, MCDA is employed to rank feasible microgrid CEC topologies and simultaneously evaluate a wide range of technical, economic, environmental, and societal design criteria. Additionally, for the purpose of increasing robustness of the proposed methodology, a sensitivity analysis of all critical parameters is needed through employment of stochastic models for renewable energy generation and end user consumption¹.

Herein, we summarize the design criteria into four general categories as follows.

- Technical criteria: Loss of Power Supply Probability (LPSP), Wasted energy
- Financial criteria: Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), Operational Expenditure (OPEX), Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Payback Period (PP)
- Environmental criteria: Greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, NO_x, SO_x)
- Social/Economic/Political criteria: Fuel Reserve Years, Job creation, Intercountry energy dependence etc.

When it comes to design constraints, various context and user-defined constraints shall be considered. The former represents renewable energy harvesting potential, applicable energy pricing policy, space availability and orientation for deployment of energy assets etc. while the latter entails constraints in terms of energy demand and associated end user habits, demand flexibility, allowable equipment budget, etc. The following list aggregates the most influential design constraints into several categories:

- Renewable energy sources (RES) harvesting potential
- Building characteristics and space availability constraints
- Energy demand requirements
- Dynamic energy pricing
- Financing conditions
- RET equipment characteristics
- RET installation parameters

Each category entails a list of constraints, as depicted in Figure 2, which are simultaneously assessed by the proposed methodology in order to deliver optimal CEC topology and sizing. The previously elaborated design constraints, in fact, define a set of boundaries for the algorithm search space in which the optimal design solution is found. However, within this constrained space there is still a significant number of feasible design alternatives. In the following elaboration, each design alternative will be referred to as microgrid configuration and will, in fact, entail both topology and sizing of the assets within CEC.

¹ <https://www.loadprofilegenerator.de/>

Figure 2. Overview of Renewable Energy Technologies configuration design parameters

Source: Marko Batić, PhD Thesis, Software system for multi-criteria planning and management of hybrid microgrids, School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, 2018.

Given the variability of generation from renewable sources, energy demand requirements and dynamically determined energy costs, each feasible configuration is modelled, and its long-term operation is simulated/optimised. When deciding on the simulation time horizon and size of the time step resolution, several factors were considered. First, a long-term CEC performance is heavily influenced by the renewable energy harvesting potential, which implies utilization of historical meteorological conditions for a given location. Moreover, since the performance should be evaluated for the entire CEC lifetime, e.g., 20 years, the partners decided to use the so-called Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) data, which provide hourly data for averaged meteorological conditions over a relatively long period and, thus, objectively characterize the specific geographical location. Second, given the objective to establish long-term assessment of the CEC operation, the linear (or mixed integer) models of energy assets running on hourly resolution are sufficiently complex. Events such as replacement of the asset (e.g., batteries typically last for 5 years), should be also considered in the analysis.

3. Feasibility tool (Scope and services of CECs)

In this section we will describe the Excel tool that was used in CECs feasibility analysis.

Starting from the technical feasibility tool, additional information was required to pilots in order to set up the proper economic tool to evaluate NPV and IRR of the investment to develop the energy communities (see Chapter 5).

3.1 Analysis of the PERIMETER

Physical perimeters of CEC considered in the evaluation can range from: unique residential collective building, to multi-residential buildings, or multi-residential buildings and offices or processes.

Additionally, the calculation shall respect the regulations in force including

- maximum distance and/or
- maximum power of the country concerned.

In France, for example, the distance between two points of the CEC cannot exceed 2 kilometers in urban areas and 20 kilometers in rural areas, but also 2 MW of total solar production power.

The figure below represents an energy community study where each green dot represents a building in the CEC-2 area. The size of the dot is not proportional to the number of dwellings.

Figure 3. Energy community study

Source: ALB Excel with add-on MapXL.

The determination of the scope must consider also the objectives of supplying local energy to the participants in the community. For example, the average French consumption per dwelling is 5 MWh of electricity per year. The perimeter of the community will have to take this data into account in the calculation of the overall CEC objective (reducing energy costs by local consumption of energy).

In any case, according to the chosen scope, it will be necessary to assess the potential gains and the cost reduction. However, it is not necessary to manage priorities, since each participant in the community is connected to the network. By active participation (by deciding whether to consume at a given time), each participant will optimize its energy load.

By analyzing the participants social profile consumption, it would be possible to more precisely calculate the overall consumption profile. Tools such as "load profile generator" can provide consumption data see Figure below. In CEC-2 framework, the figure represents the simulation of the load curves of a couple without children, the two people working.

Figure 4. Load curves of a couple without children

Source: ALB Load behaviour analysis tool <https://www.loadprofilegenerator.de/>.

By comparison, the figure below represents the consumption of a single person.

Figure 5. Load Curve of a single person

Source: ALB Load behaviour analysis tool <https://www.loadprofilegenerator.de/>.

Such modeling is interesting for maximizing the self-consumption rate in the experimental study phases of citizen energy communities, but not in a phase of rapid deployment of CECs. Indeed, the request for reduction of greenhouse gas emissions requires moving quickly from using fossil fuel consumption to participating in a citizen energy community.

Each social profile presents a different consumption curve. In our opinion, the CEC self-consumption rate will increase as the number of participants increases.

In order to achieve better return of investment, it is mandatory to adapt the perimeter of the CEC (multi-building self-consumption) with the solar energy plant size.

3.2 Analysis of SERVICES

The first service that an energy community shall provide to the participants is to stabilize a part of the energy costs. In addition, a “complementary” service needed is the one aimed at improving their autonomy and thus increasing automatically their sobriety.

However, these two main services can be supplemented with additional energy efficiency services (for systems or the building envelope), e.g., in the case of a renovation project. In the case of a new project, the design of the energy systems must consider the possibility of storing heat or cold within the building systems. To summarize, main services provided by an energy community are:

- Stabilization of energy costs
- Sobriety – autonomy – independence
- System/envelope efficiency

Ideally, a feasibility tool must make it possible to evaluate the performance of each of these services.

3.3 Stabilization of energy costs

The economic model of self-consumption can be represented as follows:

Source: ALB French economic model.

Of course, this economic model will have to be adapted to each country with regional data. This simplified economic model does not include investment costs or local investment aid but considers the day-to-day operation of self-consumption. In addition, self-consumption must be shared between the different participants in a fair manner.

Observing this diagram, we can conclude that the injection into the network must be minimized as much as possible in favor of self-consumption. The added value of creating or expanding an energy community was assessed considering avoided costs (from self-consumption) and direct revenues (from grid injection) as well as incentives, if present alongside to the evaluation of energy efficiency interventions in one of the pilots.

Figure 7. CEC economic model financial impact

Source: ALB CEC model analysis.

3.4 Sobriety – autonomy – independence

In the work “Dynamiques et solidarités à l’oeuvre dans les communes rurales Laure Dobigny”, the author clearly shows the desire of the participants to federate around energy, to work together and to go beyond a certain energy autonomy.

At the time of its development, the authors described the project as a “crazy” and “surrealist”.

- “For a project like that, you need a little bit of idealism. That is to say that if this technical choice is based, in the discourse of the actors, on objective motivations (economic, ecological and social), it is nonetheless the support of ideals. In this sense, we postulate that the goal is not energy autonomy. It is therefore rather autonomy in the sense of "doing it yourself", an appropriation of the energy tool. It is an ideal that is pursued rather than consumption on a Linky meter.”

Implementing such assessment as a service is, of course, difficult using a simple Excel table. However, a holistic community management tool should allow us to measure the real activity, and therefore, the interaction of the participants within the community.

3.5 System efficiency / envelope

The building stock in Europe is largely made up of residential buildings (75%) of which more than 70% is privately owned and occupied by owners.

Figure 8. Building Stock in EU

Source: Study of the implementation of the zero-emission building model. UPC (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya) - Link: <https://upcommons.upc.edu/handle/2117/173241>

Therefore, the renovation of the buildings shall involve significant private funds for a return on investment that is difficult to assess. On the other hand, the increase in the cost of energy in Europe from 2021 combined with a decrease in photovoltaic installation costs very often motivates renovation projects to add a budget for solar production. The return on investment is in this case easier to achieve. The renovation shall include a deeper reflection involving a global overall of the built envelope + HVAC and DHW systems + photovoltaic solar production.

This activity linked to the creation of the energy community therefore requires energy efficiency service skills specific to design offices (example ALB is providing design services). When designing a CEC community, the approach also incorporates the choices of future energy vectors, electricity or gas. This design also requires integrating energy flexibility. Since the industrial revolution, our economic system has been based on energy stocks, infinite and inexpensive, and all energy systems have been designed on this basic axiom. However, systems must be redesigned for flow energies, integrating for example thermal (hot water) and electrical (batteries) energy storage buffers.

As we noted in the sobriety chapter above, this design must also be accompanied by a redesign of behaviours and an equitable sharing of energy.

4. Feasibility tool - Implementation aspects

The general diagram of the CEC feasibility tool is detailed below. The goal was to put the user in a mode of reflection based on the data and above all to allow the sharing of skills and the exchange around the services. The input data is annual consumption or production. The services are characterized by modifiable predefined calculation components which make it possible to evaluate the gains brought by the service.

Figure 9. Feasibility tool Functional diagram

Source: MM ALB

The objective of the tool was to produce a simple, scalable assessment of the financial, and energy gains associated with setting up a CEC. General data is energy cost and carbon emissions data specific to the region under consideration. The Excel MapXL add-on allows us to represent the CEC on an open street map.

The main constraint was to collect as little data as possible while leaving the possibility of generating new services for the communities. Of course, these new services had to bring added value.

The choice of Excel as a generic tool has been supplemented by Map XL available from www.gisxl.com.

The reflection should be conducted in this way:

Phase 1 data:

- a. What is the legal framework of the country for the creation of energy communities
- b. What data is available and potential participants
- c. Qualification of data and participants
- d. Qualification of buildings (position, consumption, use, size, etc.)
- e. What are the existing and potential production sites

Phase 2 Process data

- a. Inserting data into the calculator tool
- b. Generation of current costs
- c. Geographic Visualization Map XL

Phase 3 ESCo feasibility analysis

- a. Technical analysis of equipment
- b. Exchange with the participants
- c. Collection of sociological data
- d. Collection of operational weaknesses
- e. Elaboration of sociological and physical economic solutions
- f. Value analysis

Phase 4 community modelling

- a. Determine the perimeter
- b. Simulate self-consumption rate
- c. Assess the rate of self-production
- d. Carbon analysis
- e. Economic analysis
- f. Synthesis

4.1 Feedback on methodology and further improvement options

The feasibility tool was first tested in France on various community projects and on NEON CEC-2, the Domaine de la Source. Then it was adapted and tested on CEC-1, the pilot of Berchidda, CEC-3, the pilot of Polígono industrial Las Cabezas, and CEC-4, the pilot of Stains City.

In our opinion, the initial calculations already **generate added values** to the NEON energy communities.

4.2 Berchidda feedback feasibility tool

The knowledge transfer from ALB to R2M Energy was organized in a serial of group and individual one-to-one meetings. On request, the results of the calculation will be available and provided by R2M Energy. Small interventions were needed by ALB in a form of improvements of calculation and bug fixes.

Figure 10. Feasibility tool applied for CEC Berchidda (1) - Inputs data on CEC-01 buildings

EXISTING BUILDING DATA			
Building number	Number of Apartment (SINGLE HOUSES SO NOT APPLICABLE)	Number of people	Total electricity consumption measured (kWh)
1	1	3	4.266
2	1	4	5.860
3	1	4	2.564
4	1	3	3.837
5	1	5	1.792
6	1	2	2.027
7	1	2	3.000
8	1	3	2.513
9	1	1	2.073
10	1	3	5.776
11	1	3	6.034
12	1	4	3.279
13	1	4	1.950
14	1	2	3.000
15	1	4	2.039
16	1	2	5.129
17	1	2	2.086
18	1	2	3.990
19	1	1	3.363
20	1	2	2.427
21	1	4	1.141
22	1	4	2.484
23	1	2	3.539
24	1	1	3.427
25	1	4	3.582
26	1	2	2.249
27	1	2	3.194
28	1	3	5.296
29	1	3	3.735
30	1	5	2.669
	30	37	98.321

Source: R2M Energy – Feasibility tool

Figure 11. Feasibility tool applied for CEC Berchidda (2)

58 LEGAL STATE DATA			
59 Base data			
	Price (€/kWh)	gross (€/MWh)	Source
60	Essence - Gazoil (€/kWh)	0.09650	298 https://mercato.ilsolte26.org
41	Elec HP (€/kWh) Electricity peak price	0.55408	12 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
42	Elec HC (€/kWh) Electricity low peak price	0.32434	12 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
43	Allo produit base (€/kWh) Grid Consumption	0.13740	12 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
44	ACC Alloproduit (€/kWh) CEC Grid consumption	0.14850	12 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
45	ACC Autoproduit (€/kWh) CEC self consumption	0.02090	50 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
46	Surplus (€/kWh) Grid injection	0.16000	50 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
47	Chauffage gaz (€/kWh) heating gas	0.08513	290 https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
48			https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
49			https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
50			
51 CEC CONTROL PANEL			
52	Electric mobility rate	10 % to be modified	https://www.povtechnique.info
53	Self consumption rate	41.07 %	
54	Rate of local energy consumption	50.00 % to be modified	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
55	Self consumption volume (kWh)	41 770	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
56	Grid injection volume (kWh)	59 942	
57	Inflation rate for energy price	15 % to be modified	
58			
59			
60			
61 CEC ANALYSIS SCENARII			
kwh analysis			
	Consumption (kWh/m²/year)	EXISTING 2022 HVAC gas DHW Elec (kWh)	Scenario 1 futur FULL GAZ without CEC (kWh/m²/year)
62			
63	Grid consumption Electricity Allo Elec ECS (kWh)	2.13	29 679
64	SELF CONSUMPTION Acc Elec ECS (kWh)		9.00
65	Grid consumption Electricity Allo Elec Spécifique (kWh)	4.93	68 642
66	SELF CONSUMPTION Acc Elec Spécifique (kWh)		4.93
67	Grid consumption Electricity Allo Elec Chauffage PAC (kWh)		

Source: R2M Energy – Feasibility tool

Figure 12. Feasibility tool applied for CEC Berchidda (3)

Energy balancing		Quantity	Unit
Energy Fluxes			
$E_{prosumers}$	Electricity Consumption of prosumers	64 809	kWh/year
$E_{prod PV}$	Total Energy Production from PV	101 712	kWh/year
SC (%)	Consumption rate in PV hours production (F1+F2)	50	%
$E_{selfconsumed}$	Energy Self-consumed of prosumers	32 405	kWh/year
E_{stored}	Energy stored	37 230	kWh/year
$E_{for the REC}$	Energy for the REC	32 078	kWh/year
E_{shared}	Energy shared within the REC to the consumer	16 756	kWh/year
$E_{injected}$	Energy injected in the grid (surplus not shared)	15 322	kWh/year

Incentive		Quantity	Unit
	For energy shared within the REC (for 20years)	110	€/MWh
	For energy injected into the grid	80	€/MWh
	Dispatchment	9	€/MWh

Revenue from REC	
Energy shared	1 843 €/year
Injected into grid	1 226 €/year
Dispatchment	151 €/year
TOTAL	3 220 €/year

Non-disbursement for energy selfconsumed for prosumers	
TOTAL	17 321 €/year

Source: R2M Energy – Feasibility tool

4.3 Feasibility tool feedback Polígono industrial Las Cabezas

Two individual meetings were organized by ALB with GFM to present the feasibility tool.

The team was able to exchange their respective experiences and difficulties on the modelling of energy communities. In this case, the feasibility tool was adjusted and enable the modelling of the energy community.

This community is formed by an industrial prosumer which generates all the solar energy for the community and can also store this energy to be compensated by the rest of the consumers.

There will be a special consumer which will be an electric vehicle charger, being this the most complex consumer of this pilot.

Finally, the rest of the consumers will be residential, which will have more standardized consumption profiles.

Figure 13. Feasibility tool applied in Las Cabezas CEC (1)

EXISTING BUILDING DATA		
Stakeholder number	Type of building	Number of Apartment (NOT
1	Residential	1
2	EV end-user	1
3	Residential	1
4	Residential	1
5	Residential	1
6	EV end-user	1
7	EV Recharging point	1
8	GFM - As customer	1
9	GFM - PV generation system	1
	GFM- Storage (linked with self consumption)	1
Total building SURFACE - living surface (m ²)		10
		3936

LEGAL STATE DATA		
Base data	Unit	Price €/kWh
Essence - Gazoil (€/kWh)	€	0.18505
Electricity peak price HP (€/kWh)	€	0.89537
Electricity low peak price HC (€/kWh)	€	0.04324
Grid Consumption Allo produit base (€/kWh)	€	0.03374
CEC Grid consumption ACC Allo produit (€/kWh)	€	0.00421
CEC self consumption ACC Autoproduit (€/kWh)	€	0.00028
Grid injection (€/kWh)	€	0.07000
Gaz price for HVAC (€/kWh)	€	0.06150
Industrial/Office price of energy (€/kWh)	€	0.16200
Conversion CO ₂ (44g/mol) -> C(12g/mol) - 1kg CO ₂ = 12/44 kg C		

CEC CONTROL PANEL	
Electric mobility rate (%)	3 %
Self consumption rate (%)	48.66 %
Rate of local energy consumption (%)	60.91 %
Self consumption volume (kWh)	49,218
Grid injection volume (kWh)	9,646
Inflation rate for energy price	15 %

Source: GFM – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC03 Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas
 Energy prices from: ESIOS; Fuels prices from: datos.gob.es; Other prices from: mincotur.gob.es

Figure 14. Feasibility tool applied in Las Cabezas CEC (2)

Source: Victron VRM Self-monitoring Platform – CEC03 Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas

4.4 Feasibility tool feedback Stains City

Two meeting one-to-ones were organised between SIF and ENGIE to present both the technical and economic feasibility tools. All the information was gathered in the spreadsheet and set the ground for the evaluation of the future pilot CEC-4.

Additional services will be implemented in the future and will strengthen the feasibility of the project even more.

Figure 15. Feasibility tool applied in Stains CEC (1)

EXISTING BUILDING DATA							
Building number	Number of Apartment (SINGLE HOUSES SO NOT APPLICABLE)	Number of people	Total electricity consumption measured (kWh)	Total DHW electricity consumption calculated (kWh)	Total SPECIFIC electricity consumption calculated (kWh)	Energy for Heating (Gaz) (kWh)	Total consumption Energy for Mobility calculated (kWh)
1	1	230	362.300	83.020	279.280		6.781
2	1	240	289.800	86.630	203.171		6.781
Total	2	470	652.100	169.649	482.451		13.562
SURFACE (m ² HAB) Habitable surface	11000			169.649	241.225		1

LEGAL STATE DATA			
Base data	Price €/kWh	geoCO2/kWh(1)	Source
Fsence - Gazoil (€/kWh)	0.05650	208	https://mercato.ilsola3d.net/materia-primaria/commodities/naturalia/BRNST IDF

Source: ENGIE – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CECO 1 Stain

Future energy services such as HVAC system optimization and control, EV charging from clean resources and energy electricity compensation with H2 storage during the off PV production period may be evaluated in the future using the same tool defined in this task.

Figure 16. Upcoming and future services in Stains CEC (1)

CEC energy services being Implemented	
Energy Service	Collective-self- consumption
Description	This service aims to Provide STAIN CITY CEC the surplus photovoltaic produced by INDUSTREET
Key partners	DSO: ENEDIS , Legal and operational experts for setting up the CEC , Monitoring platform editor,
Needed Technical resources	photovoltaic panels, power and telecommunication network, monitoring platform (all set-up)
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSO Fees related to the power grid connection, • Access to the monitoring platform (licenses, annual cost, admin vs, users,,,) including problem solving, maintenance, evolutions, • Photovoltaic infrastructure amortization
Potentien revenue streams	energy exchange (electricity created by CRIGEN from Hydrogen)
CEC future energy services	
Energy Service	HVAC system optimization and control
Description	Optimize the operation of the HVAC system to reduce consumption while ensuring the occupant comfort,
Key partners	BMS manufacturers and integrators ,Mtair, Soltherm
Needed resources	IT infrastructure, BMS, dashboards,
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources (development, after-sales service, etc.) • BMS integrator services • IT infrastructure
Potentien revenue stre	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Savings on the energy bill • Reuse of the service and algorithms in a business context outside CEC,
Energy Service	EV charging from clean resources
Description	EVs charging stations from renewable energies and available for the needs and usage of the CEC (charging VE, training, etc.) , and to provide flexibility to CEC by allowing the use EVs charged with excess PV energy,
Key partners	Parking space promoter , Manufacturer/ supplier and installer of the charging stations, Solution editor for the EV charging control (technical),
Needed Technical resources	Charging station, IT infrastructure, monitoring, and supervision platform, PV/H2 production, energy contracts,
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INDUSTREET PV infrastructure amortization, • Energy transformation and redistribution by ENGIE, • Legal and juridical expertise, • Creation of training supports and media • Creation of communication/promotion media • Purchase / implementation / maintenance of digital solutions (monitoring platform,,,
Potentien revenue stre	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy bill reduction • New covered period to use green energy off PV production period, • Payment for parking access and the EV charging service, • -Ultimately contribution by users (local authorities, etc.),
Energy Service	Energy electricity compensation with H2 storage during the off PV production period,
Description	Provide STAIN CITY CEC the production of Hydrogen produced and stored from INDUSTREET photovoltaic surplus production
Key pareners	Hydrogen Lab ENGIE, DSO: ENEDIS , Monitoring platform editor,
Needed Technical resources	photovoltaic panels, H2chain, power and telecommunication network, monitoring platform,
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSO Fees related to the power grid connection, • Access to the monitoring platform (licenses, annual cost, admin vs, users,,,) including problem solving, maintenance, evolutions, • Cost of the H2 chain: Production, Storage, generation, Fuel cell
Potentien revenue streams	Energy exchange (Surplus of PV production produced by INDUSTREET)

Source: ENGIE – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC0 1 Stain

4.5 Domaine de la Source

EXISTING BUILDING DATA

Building number/name	Latitude	Longitude	Type of consumption	Apartment/Office number	Potential stakeholder (number)
A	45.067909137	5.557881310	Apartment blocs	15	35
B	45.067902088	5.557997271	Apartment blocs	15	35
C	45.067944731	5.558212254	Apartment blocs	15	35
D	45.067950434	5.558996576	Apartment blocs	1	4
E	45.071502874	5.551051330	Offices	1	10
F			Apartment blocs	22	42
G			Apartment blocs	22	42
H			Apartment blocs	20	39
I			Apartment blocs	20	38
J			Apartment blocs	20	44
K			Apartment blocs	20	49
L			Apartment blocs	18	50
TOTAL				189	421

LEGAL STATE DATA

Unit	Price €/kWh	#SEC02/(kWh)	Source
Gas for mobility (€/kWh)	€	0.18784	298 https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/plan-des-energies
Electricity peak price HP (€/kWh)	€	0.14490	12 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
Electricity low peak price HC (€/kWh)	€	0.11490	12 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
Grid Consumption base (€/kWh)	€	0.13740	12 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
CEC Grid consumption (€/kWh)	€	0.14350	12 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
CEC self consumption (€/kWh)	€	0.01090	90 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
Grid injection (€/kWh)	€	0.09800	90 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/ger/ia/ICRPE
Gas HVAC (€/kWh)	€	0.08100	290 https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/ger/ia/ICRPE
Industrial/office price of energy (€/kWh)	€	0.06000	

CEC CONTROL PANEL

Electric mobility rate (%)	40 % to be modified	https://www.polechaleur-normandie.com/fr
Self consumption rate (%)	86 %	
Rate of local energy consumption (%)	90.00 % to be modified	https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
Self consumption volume (kWh)	499 988	https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
Grid injection volume (kWh)	-72 787	https://www.lefrance.gouv.fr/download/pdf
Inflation rate for energy price	1% to be modified	

CEC SERVICES ANALYSIS

Unit	Consumption analysis				
	EXISTING 2022 Consumption (kWh/m²/ab)	EXISTING 2022 HVAC gas (DHW, Elec) (kWh)	Service 1: Full GAZ without CEC (kWh/m²/ab)	Service 1: Full GAZ without CEC (kWh)	
Grid consumption Electricity, DHW, kWh		29.63	412 292	9.00	125 226
SELF consumption Electricity, DHW, kWh					
Grid consumption Electricity, DHW, kWh		83.87	453 186	83.87	453 186

Source: ALB – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Domaine de la Source

Source: ALB – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Domaine de la Source

4.6 Necessary improvements

Currently, the proposed tool does not consider the legal limits of the geographical perimeter, nor the functional mix of the community, nor the possible flexibility of the occupants, and other social and environmental factors. These aspects, as well as a larger library of service calculation components will be added later during the NEON project.

5. Economic feasibility

5.1 Introduction to the work

The analysis carried out by the partners involved in this task led the workflow towards feasible instruments and KPIs to assess the success of future energy communities in NEON. The partners' meeting addressed several barriers and crossroads that will be presented below.

The first question was to identify three aspects: WHO, WHAT, and WHEN. Whose point of view NEON was looking at, which services for each pilot CECs would have been evaluated, and which was the time horizon to be analysed. Namely, the economic feasibility analysis could have been about: ESCOs supporting the creation or the expansion of a CEC; private investors funding private citizens or ESCOs for energy efficiency interventions of new energy services; governments interested in bolstering a favourable and supporting framework for energy communities; marginal potential member interested in joining a CEC. Choosing one way or another would have changed the shape of the workflow and the data to be collected and analysed. The consortium chose to run the analysis from the point of view of the energy communities themselves, estimating the net present value (NPV) and the internal rate of return (IRR) of the different sets of investments for each pilot area, focusing on RES and energy usage optimization through battery energy storage systems (BESS).

Indeed, the opportunity to run a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) of creating new communities was out of scope and too complex for the resources available for the partners. The scientific community is still struggling in applying CBA to energy communities due to the interconnection and overlapping of a multitude of factors and potential impacts to consider. For the same reason, MCDA was shelved as well. These both represent a potential expansion of the project in the future.

This led to the exclusion from the analysis of all the non-economic factors, out of respect for their complexity, which is of course quite relevant in evaluating the impact of energy communities on individuals and territories. Environmental and social factors would be crucial in the expansion of the economic model defined, to amplify the positive results beyond the reduction of costs.

Based on the data collected in the technical feasibility analysis, SIF set up several one-to-one meetings with CECs pilot leaders to identify actual and future scenarios for CEC01-Berchidda, CEC02-Domaine de la Source, CEC03-Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas and CEC04-Stains City.

The subchapters below will describe the different analysis and will show the results for each of them.

5.2 Analysis of different scenarios in the CECs involved

As mentioned, the pilot areas are in different stages of maturity: CEC01 (BERCHIDDA in Italy) and CEC04 (STAINS CITY in France) are already operational, CEC02 (Domaine de la Source in France) will be formed in January 2023, while CEC03 (Polígono industrial Las Cabezas in Spain) is still in the planning phase.

This implied different services and investments required (see the following paragraphs) to be considered in evaluating the economic feasibility of future CECs. Given the heterogeneous scenario, the case studies' feasibility was run considering the Net present value (NPV) and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) for each pilot.

We use these two formulae, linked with one another, to calculate the current value of the future stream of payments from the investment that the different CECs will implement. For these reasons, new PV systems and BESS installed were analysed within a lifetime of 20 years, identifying investment costs and future cash flows and choosing a cautious discount rate to assess the model.

The analysis is based on the positivity of the NPV which means its rate of return will be above the discount rate and the investment is worth to be done.

Before just applying the NPV and IRR formulae we defined how members participating in the energy community may benefit from financial gains in relation to energy costs. These can include a reduction in their energy bill, both on energy costs and tax and levies reduction, and revenue coming from surplus energy injected into the grid whit feed-in-tariffs. Other benefits may include lower network tariffs due to aggregation effects (Abada, Ehrenmann, and Lambin, 2017). A community may also ensure better local supply security in case of power disturbances elsewhere in the grid (Pahkala, Uimonen, and Väre, 2018). Many examples of literature case studies highlight economic gains in the form of lower energy prices [6].

A self-consumption rate per scenario was defined, by mutual agreement with the pilot leaders, to take into account future CECs characteristics and conditions.

A common model was identified to evaluate the economic feasibility of energy communities in the context of NEON, facing several difficulties related to the complexity and heterogeneity of the topic. Various assumptions were required, as will be shown in the presentation of the model used.

5.3 The model

As mentioned above, the evaluation will consider a 20-year time horizon, to have a cautious estimation of risks and revenues related to energy services offered in NEON.

The discount rate was identified accordingly. Since it should reflect the cost of capital or the returns available on alternative investments with comparable risk, a 6.5% rate was selected analysing crowdfunding and equity investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy sources, to maintain a prudential approach.

After identifying the scenarios of production and self-consumption, the first step was to identify future investments related to the creation of a citizen energy community: new PV systems, smart meters, BESS, ICT platform, EV charging points, and energy efficiency interventions.

Characteristics of new PV systems - and especially the productivity rate (KWh/year per kWp) - were analysed through the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) of the Joint Research Center of the European Commission¹.

Concerning BESS, one cycle of charge and discharge per day was assumed, fostering the volume of daily self-consumption during low peak hours. In the model, energy stored was calculated as the minimum between the storage capacity and the remaining production not self-consumed.

$$E_{\text{stored}} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Storage capacity} * 365 \text{ days} \\ E_{\text{TOT},t} (\text{not self - consumed}) \end{array} \right.$$

To take into account the efficiency loss of the system, a degradation rate of 2% per year after the first three years was chosen, combining data from the scientific literature, inputs from NEON partners and pilot leaders and a prudential approach in the economic feasibility evaluation. This will impact also the variable costs related to Operation and Maintenance (O&M), assumed to be increasing by 0.5% every two years due to the maintenance of systems and infrastructure starting from the second year.

The implementation of the identified services will create revenue streams of avoided costs (non-disbursement) due to energy produced and self-consumed by prosumers in place of grid consumption, including the energy stored in BESS and used for EV charging.

Not knowing the distribution of consumption during the day but only the annual average, these costs were valued at the fixed market price. System charges and taxes were not considered, as well as energy incentives and subsidies, due to their volatility and unpredictability over time.

The revenues that came out were summed up with the positive cash flow linked to the electricity injected into the grid if any.

To calculate the revenue streams within the different scenarios, SIF estimated the evolution of energy prices in the period 2023-2043. Based on the analysis of the Eurostat time series, a coefficient of variation of prices in the future (beta) was identified through a linear projection. The dataset was the gross energy prices time series 2008-2021, for households' consumption between 2500 kWh and 5000 kWh.

The beta was therefore applied to the average 2021 gross electricity price in Spain, France and Italy (see Table 4), composed of the cost of energy and its supply, network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, VAT, renewable, capacity, environmental and nuclear taxes.

2021 was chosen to rule out the bias related to the energy crisis linked to the conflict between Russia and Ukraine, which is heavily affecting the market.

The same beta was applied to estimate the evolution of the “selling price”, based on the data provided by pilot partners.

Table 4. Average 2021 gross electricity price

Electricity prices components for household consumers - Consumption from 2 500 kWh to 4 999 kWh

2021	Energy and supply	Network costs	Taxes, fees, levies and charges	Value added tax (VAT)	Renewable taxes	Capacity taxes	Environmental taxes	Nuclear taxes	Other	Total
Spain	0,1304	0,0677	0,0842	0,0299	0,0186	0,0011	0,0142	0,0000	0,0205	0,3666
France	0,0727	0,0592	0,0661	0,0280	0,0000	0,0062	0,0319	0,0000	0,0000	0,2641
Italy	0,1127	0,0461	0,0719	0,0209	0,0300	0,0000	0,0167	0,0016	0,0026	0,3025

Source: Eurostat

Selecting the price model adopted depends on different aspects, and strongly affects the analysis. The first assumption is that the energy communities participate directly in the energy market. In this case, considering network costs, taxes and levies amplify the profitability of energy communities and is aligned with the objective of maximising self-consumption to reduce the costs related to grid electricity and to protect prosumers from energy price volatility, as experienced in the last two years.

At the same time, ignoring subsidies and incentives is a precautionary choice, due to their unpredictability in the future.

On the contrary, market energy prices in the next decades will surely continue to rise, with a positive effect on the profitability of energy communities. At the same time, given the need for synthesis and robustness of the model, considering daily consumption trends was not a viable option.

The methodology used to calculate the revenue streams can also include incentives if they exist. Incentives may come from different entities: States, energy management organisations, local authorities and so on. We included in one of Berchidda’s scenarios 3 kinds of incentives: for energy shared within the REC, for energy injected into the grid, and for dispatchment.

In the next subchapter, a detailed analysis of this scenario is explained.

CEC01 – Berchidda

The economic feasibility of Berchidda pilot was tested within different scenarios. SIF and R2M Energy defined, in different one-to-one meetings, three potential changes/implementations to be tested on the economic side. Currently Berchidda pilot consists of 30 apartments on a surface of 13914 m²SHAB. R2M Energy did its first division taking into consideration that 20 of the households of the CEC had already PV systems installed.

The initial “buying price” considered the average 2021 gross electricity price in Italy, including the cost of energy and its supply, network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, VAT, renewable, capacity, environmental and nuclear taxes.

Regarding the “selling price”, in Italy, the GSE (Gestore dei Servizi Energetici - Energy Services Manager) is the only implementing body that qualifies photovoltaic plants, disburses the incentives, and performs verification and control activities. It is the second national operator for intermediated energy: it collects and places on the electricity market the energy produced by the plants and certifies the origin from renewable sources of the electricity fed into the grid. The GSE supports the production of electricity from renewable sources through various incentive mechanisms, at disposal of private subjects, companies and public administrations.

The main incentive that was used by the residents of Berchidda is the Feed-in scheme called in Italy “Scambio sul Posto” to allocate incentives to private subjects, companies and public administrations that would install a photovoltaic solar plant connected to the electricity grid, proportioned to the electricity produced. This service is a particular form of on-site self-consumption that allows electricity produced and fed into the grid at a certain point in time to be offset against electricity withdrawn and consumed at a different point in time from when the production takes place. The electricity system is therefore used as a tool for the virtual storage of electricity produced but not simultaneously self-consumed.

A necessary condition for the provision of the service is the presence of plants for the consumption and production of electricity under a single point of connection to the public grid. All energy fed into the grid by the photovoltaic system and re-powered is paid for by the GSE at a variable rate, but on average around €0.13 per kWh.

Since 1 January 2008, the GSE also activated a simplified method available to producers for the marketing of electricity produced and fed into the grid called “Ritiro Dedicato” (translatable as Dedicated Withdrawal). It consists of the sale to the GSE of electricity fed into the grid by plants that can access it, at the request of the producer and as an alternative to the free market, according to principles of procedural simplicity and applying market economic conditions. The GSE pays the producer a certain price for each kWh fed into the grid. Revenues accruing to producers from the sale of electricity to the GSE are therefore added to those earned from any incentive mechanisms except where all-inclusive fixed prices, including the incentive, are applied for the withdrawal of electricity fed into the grid.

Thanks to the entry into force of Decree-Law 162/19 (Article 42bis) and its implementing measures, such as ARERA's Resolution 318/2020/R/eel and the MiSE's Ministerial Decree of 16 September 2020, End customers, electricity consumers, can now join together to produce locally, through renewable sources, the electricity needed for their needs, 'sharing' it in the perimeter of their Renewable Energy Community. The 'shared' electricity (equal to the minimum, on an hourly basis, between the electricity fed into the grid by the production plants and the electricity withdrawn by the consumers that are relevant for the configuration) benefits from an economic contribution recognised by the GSE following access to the valorisation and incentive service.

So, when an end user decides to join a REC, he renounces his "Scambio Sul Posto" contract with the GSE and joins the community. Once he/she is a member of the CER, in addition to the rewarding incentives of 110Euro/MWh for the energy shared within the REC and of 9Euro/MWh for not paying system charges, he/she no longer adds the "Scambio Sul Posto" but the "Ritiro Dedicato". At present, there is no publicly available formula to determine the exact amount. It takes into account different variables and is proportional to the day-ahead price based on the PUN. The amount is approximately very close to the PUN of the day before.

At the end of November 2022, after Arera's initial determinations, the Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security (Mase) published the consultation on the principles for the implementation of the regulation of incentives for energy sharing under Article 8 of Legislative Decree No. 199 of 8 November 2021 (Energy Communities and Self-Consumption Systems - plants up to 1 MW). The consultation only concerns renewable energy communities and renewable self-consumers acting collectively, as it specifically deals with the subject of incentivisation of sharing carried out in such aggregations.

In a nutshell, it maintains in many respects the experimental regime currently in force while taking into account all the new parameters that were introduced at the level of legislative decrees. The incentive levels for shared energy (that will be included in the last scenario) are maintained unchanged with respect to the experimental regime (100 €/MWh for collectives of self-consumers and 110 €/MWh for REC) and with respect to their duration of 20 years. While the system of valuation of the sale of energy to the grid is also differentiated according to the level of sharing and, more precisely, in the event that the sharing is greater than 70% of the energy fed into the grid, this valuation is equal to the value assigned by the market (as it is now), while in the event that the sharing is lower than the aforementioned threshold of 70%, there is a cap on the average valuation of energy equal to 80 €/MWh.

Therefore, as a precaution, a fee of 80€/MWh is considered in the scenarios as a contribution for energy fed into the grid and a "selling price" of €0,08 per kWh is used in the model.

The first implemented scenario regards the investment in 10 new PV systems to be installed in the rest of the households of the Berchidda pilot, each with 4 kWp of installed capacity and 10 new batteries with 5,1kWh of capacity each. To calculate the NPV of the new investment of the 10 PV systems, SIF used a discount rate of 6,5% (for the reason explained above, see 5.3). The cash flows were calculated on 20 years of usage of the power plant. To include a prudential estimation of the life cycle of power plants we assumed that the plant is 100% functioning for the first 3 years and afterwards a 2% obsolescence rate per year occurs to the system. This reduces the production capacity every year. In our economic model, the data explained until now are detailed in the investment hypothesis.

The second and third parts of the table implemented for each of the scenarios is the cost analysis. Starting from the costs of the assets (Investment costs of new PV systems, smart meters, ICT platform, and BESS) and the variable and fixed operation and maintenance (O&M) costs. O&M costs, increasing by 0.5% every 2 years starting from the first year, were subtracted from the revenues to identify the annual cash flows of the investment.

In our table it was introduced the assumption of the calculation of the investment revenues. SIF calculate the revenue with the following formula: kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price (avoided costs due to self-consumption) + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate) *selling price (direct revenues coming from grid injection).

The four pilot CECs are quite different from each other, this calculation was a good way to have a homogenous methodology to identify the economic gains in relation to energy investments.

In both scenarios representing Berchidda, the goal was to consider different levels of self-consumption to assess the impact on profitability. In particular, the first one considers a 69% self-consumption rate, against a 71% self-consumption rate in the second one. This marginal analysis aimed at considering the threshold above which “selling price” changes from the contribution for energy fed into the grid (0,08 €/kWh) to the PUN (0,1255 €/kWh, 2021 average). All the investments analysed had a positive NPV.

As already mentioned above, the first scenario sees 10 new prosumers installing a power plant of 10 PV systems and 5 new batteries. The calculation of the NPV gave a positive result of € 12.995,97 with an IRR of 8%.

Table 5. Economic analysis of Berchidda – Scenario 1

Berchidda economic analysis - Scenario 1 - self-consumption (69%)		
Investment hypothesis		
Number of new prosumers (#)	10	
Number of new PV Systems (#)	10	
Number of new BESS (#)	5	
Power of the plant (kWp)	40,00	
Berchidda's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp from PVGIS	1525,84	
Investment costs		Unit price
PV System	80000 €	2000 €/kWp
Smart meter	2500 €	250 €/Unit
Platform	2000 €	200 €/Unit
Batteries	28050 €	1100 €/kWh
Operation and Maintenance costs per year		Unit price
Maintenance systems	520 €	13 €/kWp
Maintenance infrastructure	350 €	35 €/unit
Data management	150 €	15€/unit
Administrative costs	136 €	€/year
Assumption of investment revenues		

kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price		
Discount rate	6,50%	
NPV	12.995,97 €	
IRR	8%	

Source: SIF R2M Energy – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Berchidda

The second scenario analysed the situation in which the number of prosumers in the CEC was highly increased with 80 new participants in the CEC, and, as in the previous case, with a new PV plant installation. The 80 PVs installed had a productivity of 320 kWp. Moreover, 40 batteries with a 5,1 kWh capacity each were included in this scenario.

Using the same estimated prices of the first scenario and a self-consumption rate of 71% the result was a positive NPV of €201.110,70 and an IRR of 9%. The result showed that increasing the prosumers, PV power plant, BESS installed and most of all the self-consumption rate will have a positive impact on the investment side as well. Exceeding the 70% threshold of self-consumption amplifies the positive return related to the surplus in consumption injected into the grid that is now sold at a price equal to the value assigned by the market (0,1255 €/kWh, average 2021 PUN).

Table 6. Economic analysis of Berchidda – Scenario 2

Berchidda economic analysis - Scenario 2 – self-consumption (71%)		
Investment hypothesis		
Number of new prosumers (#)	80	
Number of new PV Systems (#)	80	
Number of new Bess (#)	40	
Power of the plant (kWp)	320	
Berchidda's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp from PVGIS	1525,84	
Investment costs		Unit price
PV System	640000 €	2000 €/kWp
Smart meter	20000 €	250 €/Unit
Platform	16000 €	200 €/Unit
Batteries	224400 €	1100 €/kWh
Operation and Maintenance costs per year		Unit price
Maintenance systems	4160 €	13 €/kWp
Maintenance infrastructure	2800 €	35 €/unit
Data management	1200 €	15€/unit

Administrative costs	928 €	€/year
Assumption of investment revenues		
kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price		
Discount rate	6,50%	
NPV	201110,70 €	
IRR	9%	

Source: SIF R2M Energy – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Berchidda

The analysis of the two scenarios of Berchidda showed the positive impact that self-consumption has on the CEC. In the future, more scenarios with the introduction of other energy efficiency measures will be implemented and they could be assessed with the method analysed until now.

CEC02 - Domaine de la Source

After a mail correspondence and two one-to-one meetings with ALB, SIF conducted the economic analysis of 2 different scenarios.

In Domaine de la Source's case, the prosumers taken into account are 25 and the actual PV system has a 45 kWp capacity without BESS, like in STAINS CITY, check CEC04 below.

In this case, the first scenario considers only energy efficiency interventions regarding DHW usage. In Domaine de la Source, the total electricity consumption is 164.83 MWh/year for 25 dwellings. 64% of the electricity is used for DHW, 18% for HVAC, and specific usages (lighting-domestic usage) represent 18% of the total.

The 25 dwellings are not occupied all the time during the year, since only 5 to 10 apartments are used all over the year. The hot water system is centralized, and it was designed for 100% full-time occupancy. This results in power consumption inefficiencies to be tackled, and energy efficiency interventions are needed. Local DHW boiler installation, for example, could guarantee a 20% reduction in consumption per apartment.

Albedo is actually planning an accurate investigation and setting of new measurement sensors for DHW, with a cost of €3000. Depending on the measurement results and the usage evaluation (thanks to smart meter data) Albedo will be able to identify the best options and to work on:

1. automatic planning of DHW production and/or
2. small local DHW boilers installation in the apartments and/or
3. implementation of intelligent AI DHW control (with a cost of €8500)

We assumed that all the interventions will be realised. Depending on the technology used, the overall investment cost could fall in the range between 15.000 and 50.000€. Given the kind of apartments, in size and oldness, a small investment dimension was chosen, considering €1.660 of investment per apartment, for a total cost of €41.500.

The initial cost of a local DHW boiler is higher with respect to a conventional storage water heater, but it will typically last longer (20 years or more) with lower operating and energy costs (between €40 and €185 on average¹). This could offset the higher installation price.

Preventive maintenance should be performed twice annually by a professional, therefore Scenario 2 considered a yearly average of €120 operation and maintenance cost, with a 0.5% increase every 4 years to consider the obsolescence of the water heater.

The scenario forecasts a negative -2.692,05 NPV. This result is aligned with the NEON concept, underlining that energy efficiency interventions alone are not enough to ensure profitability: CECs are crucial to support citizens, in order to maximise self-consumption rates and therefore the benefits for the members.

Table 7. Economic analysis of Domaine de la Source – Scenario 1

Domaine de la Source economic analysis - Scenario 1 - DHW efficiency intervention		
Investment hypothesis		
Number of prosumers (#)		25
Number of new Local DHW boiler		25,00
Investment costs		Unit price
Local DHW boiler	25000	1000
DHW sensor	3000	
Change in the DHW process (pumps, tank storage, ...)	5000	
AI DHW control platform	8500	
Operation and Maintenance costs		Unit price
Water heater maintenance	2500	100
Assumption of investment revenues		
Energy savings (energy efficiency)*Price buying		
Discount rate		6,50%
NPV		-2.692,05
IRR		6%

Source: SIF ALB – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Domaine de la Source

As a second scenario, SIF investigates the possibility of Domaine de la Source to enlarge the community to the city of Villard de Lans, adding 200 new prosumers and PV systems with a total productivity of 800 kWp, without BESS.

The cost of the power plant and the Platform was added with Fixed yearly maintenance costs that we increased every 2 years of +0,5%.

The revenues were calculated, as for the other CECs, summing the avoided costs coming from self-consumption to the revenues from the energy injected into the GRID.

The selected “buying and selling” prices were respectively €0, € 0,2641 and €0,10, and were increasing by 0,1% every year.

The initial “buying price” considered the average 2021 gross electricity price in France, including the cost of energy and its supply, network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, VAT, renewable, capacity, environmental and nuclear taxes. The “selling price” of each kWh injected depends on the solar self-consumption installed. The general price depends on the power reached with each PV installed. When the power production of a PV is lower than 9 kWp the energy selling price is €0,10, while if the production is higher than 9kWp per PV installed, the price drops to €0,06.

In Domaine de la Source scenario the selling price used was €0,10 because it was estimated a power of 4KWp for each PV installed.

Taking as assumption an obsolescence rate of 2% each year after the first 3 years of usage of the power plant, SIF computed a positive NPV of 315.155 and an IRR of 9,3%.

The CEC will have a self-consumption rate of 64% and sell the rest of the energy to the grid.

Table 8. Economic analysis of Domaine de la Source – Scenario 2

Domaine de la Source economic analysis Scenario 2 - self-consumption (64%)		
Investment hypothesis		
Number of new prosumers (#)	200	
Number of new PV Systems (#)	200	
Number of new Bess (#)	-	
Power of the plant (kWp)	800,00	
Domaine's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp	1.189,13	
Investment costs		Estimation of unit price
PV System	1444800	1806
Smart meter	40000	200
Platform	4320	21,6
Batteries	-	-

Operation and Maintenance costs	Fixed price	
Maintenance systems	9000	
Maintenance infrastructure		
Data management		
Administrative costs	1000	
Assumption of investment revenues		
kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price.		
Discount rate	6,50%	
NPV	315.155,31	
IRR	9,3%	

Source: SIF ALB – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Domaine de la Source

The increased positive result in second Scenario shows the additional impact of enhancing and expanding the energy community, amplifying effectiveness of energy efficiency interventions. It will be further enriched in the future with several ancillary services that could bring even more savings.

CEC03 - Polígono industrial Las Cabezas

Polígono industrial Las Cabezas differs from the other pilot CECs since it is considering both residential and industrial prosumers, intending to expand the future energy community by considering investments in new PV plants, BESS, and EV charging stations. In the future, an assessment of new wind turbine investments should be added to the model.

Having this in mind, SIF met GFM in four one-to-one meetings to start shaping two possible scenarios to be tested.

As already seen with the previous CECs, the revenues of the investment are calculated as the sum of avoided costs related to self-consumption and the direct revenues coming from the energy sold to the grid.

SIF and GFM identified a first scenario with the introduction of 6 new prosumers, 6 new PV systems installed with a productivity of 30 kWp and 3 batteries with 5 kWh of capacity per each. For the residential end-users, the buying prices used are around 0,3666 €/kWh. These prices are the average 2021 gross electricity price in Spain, including the cost of energy and its supply, network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, VAT, renewable, capacity, environmental and nuclear taxes.

In order to evaluate the energy surplus injected into the grid, the simplified compensation mechanism can be considered. It establishes the price of each kWh injected as long as it is from

a solar self-consumption installation. This compensation is made monthly as a rule. The general price of compensation will depend on the commercial agreement reached, although the average is normally around 0.08-0.1 €/kWh. For a prudent and resilient model, a 0,8 €/kWh selling price was considered.

Considering the number of PVs and BESS installed, an estimation of fixed O&M costs was added, with an increasing rate of 0,5% every two years starting from the first year. The forecasted self-consumption rate is 65%. Following the same steps as the previous CECs, cash flows were calculated. Using a discount rate of 6,5%, a positive NPV of €4.217 and an IRR of 8% emerged.

Table 9. Economic analysis of Polígono industrial Las Cabezas – Scenario 1

Polígono industrial Las Cabezas - Economic analysis scenario 1 - Self-consumption (65%)		
Investment hypothesis		
Number of new prosumers (#)	6	
Number of new PV Systems (#)	6	
Number of new Bess (#)	3	
Power of the plant (kWp)	30,00	
Polígono's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp from PVGIS	1.736,96	
Investment costs	Total investments costs	Unit price
PV System	45000 €	1500 €/W
Smart meter	1500 €	250 €/Unit
Platform	600 €	100 €/Unit
Batteries	12000 €	800 €/kWh
Operation and Maintenance costs per year	Price	Unit price
Maintenance systems	1800 €	60 €/kWp
Maintenance infrastructure	3000 €	500 €/Unit
Data management	1200 €	200 €/Unit
Administrative costs	500€	€/year
Assumption of investment revenues		
kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price		
Discount rate	6,50%	
NPV	4.217 €	
IRR	8%	

Source: SIF GFM – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Polígono industrial Las Cabezas

A second scenario was implemented, considering peculiarities Polígono industrial Las Cabezas. The hypothesis was the following:

10 new prosumers
10 PV systems (6*5kWp + 4*10kWp)
- 6 residential prosumers (4 batteries 5kWh per each)
- 4 industrial prosumers (4 batteries, 8kWh per each)

Source: SIF GFM – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Polígono industrial Las Cabezas

The total capacity of the new PV systems was 70 kWp, corresponding to a total RES production of 121587,2 kWh/year. New BESS capacity corresponded to 53 kWh.

In this scenario, costs and revenues accounted for the difference in prices related to the residential or industrial characteristics of prosumers.

While the estimated buying prices of 0,3666 €/kWh for residential end-users was kept, the price for industrial consumers was different. In many cases, these consumers may even have their offer for intra-day markets, for example, if they are very large consumers (or associations of them, as would be the trading companies). For these reasons, the average 2021 gross electricity price for non-household consumers (consuming less than 10MWh) in Spain was considered, including the cost of energy and its supply, network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, VAT, renewable, capacity, environmental taxes: 0,3759 €/kWh. The grid injection price was considered the same as the first scenario for both kinds of prosumers.

Table 10. Gross electricity price for non-household consumers (consuming < 10MWh) in Spain

Electricity prices components for non-household consumers - Consumption less than 20 MWh									
2021	Energy and supply	Network costs	Taxes, fees, levies and charges	Value added tax (VAT)	Renewable taxes	Capacity taxes	Environmental taxes	Other	Total
Spain	0,0901	0,0690	0,1084	0,0367	0,0230	0,0011	0,0075	0,0401	0,3759

PV and BESS installation costs vary as well, depending on the kind of prosumer.

For example, the costs of new PV systems depend mostly on the power to be installed. For the year 2023, prices for residential installations are estimated to be around 1.8-1.2 €/Wp2.

For industrial consumers or large installations, the price will generally be lower, except in very particular cases where there are major architectural or logistical challenges. For cases of a higher power, prices of around 0.8 - 0.65 €/kWp can be considered.

For batteries, it is also possible to experience scalability due to a rappel in the volume of the installation. The costs for a residential user, working together with a solar inverter, could be defined as about 800 €/kWh, whereas in the case of stationary batteries of large capacities, the price would be slightly lower, being able to reach prices of around 600 €/kWh in the best case. In Scenario 2 estimation we consider a common price of 800 €/kWh.

	Residential	Industrial	Unit
PV system kWp	5	10	kWp
Total kWp installed	30	40	kWp
PV system unit cost	1500	750	€ kWh/year
BESS unit capacity	5	8	kWh
Total BESS capacity	20	32	kWh
BESS unit cost	800	800	€/kWh

Energy distribution generally depends on the power consumed and when this power is used.

Generally, industries and undertakings usually install a power equal to the nominal energy consumption or higher, while in the residential sector, thanks to the compensation, it is not necessary to exceed the contracted power.

If we look at consumption values, they are normally directly proportional to the installed capacity of RES (except in particular cases, but this would require a specific and much more detailed study) so we can take advantage of the same distribution for the energy consumed as for the power of the PV installations.

For this reason, if out of the total of new 70kWp to be installed, 30kWp are from residential consumers, this represents approximately 40% of the consumption. The remaining 60% will be industrial consumption.

In this framework, the scenario led us to a positive NPV of € 80.967 and an IRR of 15%.

Table 11. Economic analysis of Polígono industrial Las Cabezas – Scenario 2

Polígono industrial Las Cabezas - Economic analysis scenario 2 - Self-consumption (61%)		Unity cost	
Investment hypothesis			
Number of new prosumers (#)	10		

Number of new PV Systems (#)	10		
Number of new Bess (#)	8		
Power of the plant (kWp)	70,00		
Polígono's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp from PVGIS	1.736,96		
Investment costs		Residential	Industrial
PV System	75000	1500 €/kWp	750 €/kWp
Smart meter	2500	250 €/Unit	250 €/Unit
Platform	1000	100 €/Unit	100 €/Unit
Batteries	41600	800 €/kWh	800 €/kWh
Operation and Maintenance costs per year	Fixed price		Unit price
Maintenance systems	4000 €		100 €/kWp
Maintenance infrastructure	3332 €		833 €/Unit
Data management	1332 €		333 €/Unit
Administrative costs	900 €		€/year
Assumption of investment revenues			
kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price.			
Discount rate	6,50%		
NPV	80.967 €		
IRR	15%		

Source: SIF GFM – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Polígono industrial Las Cabezas

The presence of industrial or commercial prosumers enhances the positive impact of the investment, with a higher NPV with respect to the first scenario.

In the future to complete the analysis and reach the objective set up by Polígono industrial Las Cabezas at the beginning of the project it will be possible to add within this model the other costs and energy production revenues from the wind turbines and the costs to set EV charging points.

CEC04 – Stains City

The situation for Stains City was a bit different from the others, in fact, they have already different energy efficiency measures implemented in the pilot site and a self-consumption rate that is already at 80%. After different meetings between ENGIE and SIF, two scenarios were defined. With respect to the other pilots, Engie collaborates with Enogrid for the management of the platform and the self-consumption, with related costs, detailed in the following summary tables. The platform costs €472/year/user and will be considered in the following scenarios. The “buying prices” are the average 2021 gross electricity price in France, including the cost of energy and its supply, network costs, taxes, fees, levies and charges, VAT, renewable, capacity, environmental and nuclear taxes.

To understand what really happens when a CEC like Stains City is at his beginning phase, a scenario in which 2 new prosumers join the community was created. In this scenario there are 2 new PV systems with a productivity of 150 kWp and no battery system. The self-consumption rate will be 70%, there will not be injection fees since there is no injection into the grid.

Again, buying prices are the average 2021 gross electricity price, while the selling prices remains the same. The actualization of the cash flows with the discount rate of 6,5% brought the NPV to became 98.146 with a 14% IRR.

Table 12. Economic analysis of Stains City – Scenario 1

Stain city economic analysis scenario 1 - self consumption (70%)		
Investment hypotesis		
Number of new prosumers (#)	2	
Number of new PV Systems (#)	2	
Number of new Bess (#)	-	
Power of the plant (kWp)	150,00	
Stain City's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp from PVGIS	1128,03	
Investment costs		Unit price
PV System	172500,00	1150
Smart meter	500	250
Batteries	0	0
Energy injection fees	0	
Operation and Mantainace costs		
Maintenance systems	1950	13
Maintenance infrastructure	5250	35
Data management	30	15
Enogrid platform	944	472
Assumption of investment revenues		

kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price		
Discount rate		6,50%
NPV		€ 98.146
IRR		14%

Source: SIF ENGIE – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Stain

In the second scenario, the hypothesis implies two new prosumers with 150kWp of new PV already installed, two new consumers with similar electric needs and one BESS of 100kWh. Cost structure remains the same.

With the usual prices and a self-consumption rate of 70%, the scenario shows positive results with a €69.812,59 NPV and an IRR of 11%.

Table 13. Economic analysis of Stains City – Scenario 2

Stain city economic analysis scenario 3 - self consumption (70%)		
Investment hypotesis		
Number of new prosumers (#)		4
Number of new PV Systems (#)		4
Number of new Bess (#)		1
Power of the plant (kWp)		150,00
Stain City's productivity (kWh /year) per kWp from PVGIS		1128,03
Investment costs		Unit price
PV System	172500,00	1150
Smart meter	1000	250
Platform	1888	472
Batteries	15000	150
Energy injection fees	0,00	
Operation and Mantainace costs		
Maintenance systems	1950	13
Maintenance infrastructure	5250	35
Data management	60	15
Enogrid platform	1888	472
Assumption of investment revenues		
kWh produced*self-consumption rate*buying price + kWh produced*(1-self-consumption rate)*selling price		

Discount rate	6,50%	
NPV	€ 69.812,59	
IRR	11%	

Source: SIF ENGIE – Feasibility tool Spreadsheet – CEC Stain

The analysis shows that having similar conditions to the ones Stain city has now with an increased number of PV system and no injection into the grid will be worth it. For sure, the new technologies and services that Stains City is planning to have should be included in this schema later to assess their feasibility.

6. Conclusion

The high-level objective of NEON is to exploit building energy efficiency, renewable energy generation and storage, and demand flexibility to increase energy savings, reduce CO2 emissions, and provide cost savings across sectors. To succeed in these high-level objectives, in the first project year, the consortium conducted

- an inventory of services already existing on the CEC side (see D1.1.) and
- an inventory of services provided by technical partners that can be deployed or integrated either via CEC platforms or the example NEON platform deployed at IMP side (see D1.5).

Based on the foreseen activities in the NEON framework, the consortium took action to understand the feasibility and the KPIs of the evolving NEON energy communities. The feasibility tool proposed in Task 2.4 framework takes into consideration that one CEC can be in different establishment / operational stages and different evaluation/assessment tools for planning the next steps of CEC development will be needed.

The technical feasibility tool was first tested in France on various community projects and NEON CEC-2, the Domaine de la Source. Then it was adapted and tested all the pilot CECs. In our opinion, the initial calculations already generate added values to the NEON energy communities.

The economic scenarios analysis was differentiated for each pilot, based on the heterogeneity of the community. Indeed, they differ in terms of size, number and typology of potential members, degree of energy efficiency, PV system installed, EV charging stations, smart meters and so on. The goal was to assess the feasibility of different kinds of interventions, to address the different requirements of each pilot. Berchidda was used to evaluate the feasibility of the NEON concept on a group of 30 private buildings. Domaine de la Source is composed of 25 dwellings in 3 residential buildings, with a higher degree of energy efficiency to be reached and no PV investments foreseen. Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas allowed studying a mix of industrial and residential buildings, that requires investments in PV systems and EV charging points. In closing, Stains City shows a sample of office buildings and service areas, with a PV plant already in place and an investment related to the creation of the energy community to exploit the benefits of the role of prosumers.

The model assessed underlined the crucial role of maximising self-consumption to exploit the benefits of reducing the amount of energy bought, with related avoided costs in terms of higher market tariffs, taxes and levies. This effect is amplified when considering also non-residential prosumers, capable of differentiating the consumption profiles in the CEC. At the same time, Domain de la Source shows that energy efficiency interventions are not enough if they are not coupled with an enhancement and expansion of the energy community.

7. Relevant literature

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8. Internal Review

Internal Review 1

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SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
29	4	It would be important to include in the detailed structure of the tool also domaine de la source
34	4.5	The “necessary improvements” part needs to be implemented

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

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... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y			
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SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
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CONCLUSION

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